

Interesting species of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from China in the collection of S. Murzin. Part 1

Интересные виды жуков-усачей (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) из Китая в коллекции С. Мурзина (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). Часть 1

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, new records, China.

Abstract. 20 Cerambycidae species are newly recorded for different provinces of China, and three species, *Annamanum rondoni* Breuning, 1962, *Rhodopina albomarmorata* Breuning, 1958 and *R. pedongensis* Breuning, 1969, are recorded from China for the first time.

Резюме. В статье приводится информация о 20 видах жуков-усачей, которые впервые указываются для различных провинций Китая, а *Annamanum rondoni* Breuning, 1962, *Rhodopina albomarmorata* Breuning, 1958 и *Rhodopina pedongensis* Breuning, 1969 впервые указываются для Китая.

Introduction

Many new interesting Cerambycidae were collected all over the world by Sergey Murzin during several seasons and preserved in a private home collection, which was never systematically observed. Now we begin to study that enormous materials. The results of our investigations will be published in a series of articles.

The identification of the species were arranged by the authors. Sometimes it was kindly proved by Dr. Meiying Lin, Dr. Guanglin Xie and Dr. Junsuke Yamasako.

The distributional data for each taxon are based on the publication by Lin and Yang [2019].

All materials studied are deposited in the collection of S. Murzin (Moscow, Russia).

List of identified species

Acalolepta (Acalolepta) seunghwani
Danilevsky, 2013

Material. China: *Sichuan prov.*, 70 km W Chengdu, Qingcheng Hou Shan mts, 1500 m, 8–14.06.2005, S. and V. Murzin leg. — 1 male; 70 km W Chengdu, Qingcheng Hou Shan mts, 1500 m, 15–20.06.2005, S. and V. Murzin leg. —

1 female, (SM); Qingchenghoushan Mts, 70 km W Chengdu, 1435 m, 9–14.07.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghoushan Mts, 1400 m, 16–25.08.2005, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghoushan Mts, 1400 m, 16–25.08.2005, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghoushan Mts, 1400 m, 21–25.06.2005, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghou Shan Mts, 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 10.07.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 female; Qingchenghou Mts, 70 km W Chengdu, 1500 m, 15–18.07.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghou Mts, 70 km W Chengdu, 1500 m, 15–18.07.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghou Shan Mts, 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 15.08.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingcheng Houshan Mts, 70 km NW Chengdu, 30.9338 N, 103.4738 E, 1350 m, 6–13.08.2010, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Jilin), DPR Korea, RO Korea, Russia (Siberia).

Acalolepta (Acalolepta) vitalisi (Pic, 1925)

Material. China: *W Yunnan prov.*, 60 km E Tengchong mts, 2200 m, 19–22.05.2006, S. Murzin and I. Shokhin leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Yunnan — new record; Zhejiang, Jiangxi, Hunan, Fujian, Taiwan, Guangdong, Hainan, Guangxi, Sichuan), Vietnam, Cambodia.

Paraleprodera carolina (Fairmaire, 1900)

Material. China: *S Gansu prov.*, left bank of Yantanghe, 33°13'35" N, 104°42'29" E, 1673 m, 19.07.2004, I. Belousov, I. Kabak leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Gansu - new record; Shaanxi, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, Hubei, Jiangxi, Hunan, Fujian, Taiwan, Sichuan, Guizhou, Yunnan).

Pharsalia (Antennopharsalia) antennata
Gahan, 1894

Material. China, *Sichuan prov.*, Qingchenghou Shan Mts, 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 15.08.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Fujian, Guangxi, Yunnan), Laos, India, Myanmar.

Xenohammus bimaculatus Schwarzer, 1931

Material. China: Sichuan, 70 km W Chengdu, Qingcheng Hou Shan mts, 1500 m, 15–20.06.2005, S. and V. Murzin leg. — 1 male; Qingchenghou Shan Mts, 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 15.08.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 2 females; Baoxing env., 1200–1500 m, 14–16.07.2005, S. Murzin leg. — 1 female; Qingchenghou Shan Mts, 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 10.07.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Zhejiang, Jiangxi, Fujian, Taiwan, Guangdong, Hainan, Guangxi, Guizhou), Japan.

Uraecha yunnana Breuning, 1936

Material. China: S Gansu, S Wenxian, Shangdan, on light, 20.06.2006, Belousov and Kabak leg. — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Gansu — new record; Sichuan, Yunnan).

Menesia sulphurata (Gebler, 1825)

Material. China: Gansu prov., Min Shan Mts., 2100 m, 70 km NW Wudu, 1.06.1997, A. Gorodinsky leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Gansu — new record; Jilin, Beijing, Hebei, Shanxi, Shandong, Henan, Shaanxi, Ningxia, Hubei, Taiwan, Sichuan), Mongolia, Kazakhstan, Russia, DPR Korea, RO Korea, Japan.

Calloides magnificus (Pic, 1916)

Material. China: Gansu, Wudu, 21–24.6.2009, E. Kucera leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Gansu — new record; Hebei, Shanxi, Shandong, Shaanxi, Sichuan).

Mesosa (Aplocnemia) longipennis Bates, 1873

Material. China: Sichuan prov., Qingcheng Hou Shan mts., 70 km NW Chengdu, 1500 m, 25–31.08.2007, S. Murzin leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Yunnan).

Aethalodes verrucosus verrucosus Gahan, 1888

Material. China: Hai Nan, Mt. Wu-zhi-shan, 2–19.08.2000 — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Hainan — new record; Shaanxi, Zhejiang, Hubei, Jiangxi, Hunan, Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Sichuan, Guizhou), Vietnam.

Paramenesia subcarinata Gressitt, 1951

Material. China: Shaanxi prov., Haozhenzi env., 1350–1500 m, 14–24.06.1999, S. Murzin — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Shaanxi — new record; Hubei, Guangdong).

Exocentrus theresae Pic, 1939

Material. China: Sichuan, WSW Lixian, 5.9 km SW Shangzhai, 3025 m, 31°20'54" N, 102°50'26" E, 15.06.2016, I. Kabak, G. Davidian leg. — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Beijing).

Cleomenes longipennis longipennis Gressitt, 1951

Material. China: Gansu, 70 km W Wudu, 10.06.1997, A. Shamaev leg. — 1 male (collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow, Russia).

Distribution. China (Gansu — new records; Shaanxi, Hubei, Taiwan, Sichuan, Yunnan).

Cleomenes semiargentens Gressitt, 1945

Material. China: Shaanxi prov., Zhouzhi env., Taibaishan Nat. park, 1350 m, 30.05.1999, M. Murzin leg. — 2 females.

Distribution. China (Shaanxi — new record; Sichuan).

Cleomenes giganteus Holzschuh, 1995

Material. China: Sichuan prov., valley 5 km N Wenchuan, 2000 m, 28–30.06.2001, S. Murzin leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Yunnan).

Parechthistatus chinensis Breuning, 1942

Material. China: S Gansu prov., Tochizi, 2400 m, 33°9'21" N 105°4'48" E, 21–24.05.1997, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male, 1 female; Win Shan Mts., 2100 m, 70 km NW from Wudu, 1.06.1997, A. Gorodinsky leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Gansu — new record; Henan, Shaanxi).

Chloridolum (Leontium) tenuipes (Fairmaire, 1889)

Material. China: Sichuan, Luojishan mts., 60 km S Xichang, 25.07.1998 — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record; Guizhou, Yunnan).

Rhodopina albomarmorata Breuning, 1958

Material. China: Sichuan prov., 53 km NW Lixian, 3300–3500 m, 07.2001, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Sichuan — new record), India: Sikkim and Darjeeling district, Nepal.

Rhodopina pedongensis Breuning, 1969

Material. China: Yunnan prov., 54 km E Tengchong, 2150 m, 4–9.09.2004, S. Murzin leg. — 1 female.

Distribution. China (Yunnan — new record), India: Sikkim and Darjeeling district.

Annamanum rondoni Breuning, 1962

Material. S. China: Yunnan prov., Xiquanbanna, Guanping env., 60 km N Jinghong, 1000 m, 28–30.IV.2003, S. Murzin leg. — 1 male.

Distribution. China (Yunnan — new record).

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